

AI CHATBOT BASED COLLABORATION TREATMENT

Narayanan C*, Narmatha E**, Pavithra K**, Priyadharshini R P**
& Selvalakshmi A**

* Professor, Department of Bio Medical Engineering, Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College (Autonomous), Perambalur, Tamil Nadu

** UG Student, Department of Bio Medical Engineering, Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College (Autonomous), Perambalur, Tamil Nadu

Cite This Article: Narayanan C, Narmatha E, Pavithra K, Priyadharshini R P & Selvalakshmi A, "AI Chatbot Based Collaboration Treatment", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, International Peer Reviewed - Refereed Research Journal, Volume 9, Issue 1, January - June, Page Number 56-60, 2024.

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Abstract:

This paper aims to develop a Chatbot-based system for Naturopathy and Siddha treatment and incorporating features for booking doctor appointments. The chatbot will provide solution based on their symptoms and the method chosen by the user. Users will be able to interact with the chatbot through text commands, for accessing the medical information either from Naturopathy or Siddha treatment method. In this method we have incorporated contact facility to get an appointment for proper treatment to the major problems and also the users and doctors can fix the schedule based on their availability mutually. In the AI tool, the user language is converted into machine language by the technique of Natural Language Processing (NLP). The Accuracy and Effectiveness are improved based on the user interaction and usage of the facility.

Key Words: Chatbot-Based System, Doctor Appointment, Naturopathy and Siddha Treatment, Voice Command, Accuracy, Location.

1. Introduction:

The proposed paper aims to revolutionize the way naturopathy and siddha treatment is accessed and delivered by developing a sophisticated chatbot-based system. This system will not only provide personalized Naturopathy and Siddha treatment recommendations but also offer convenient features for booking doctor appointments. Naturopathy and Siddha, as a holistic approach to healthcare, emphasizes natural remedies and treatments tailored to individual needs. However, accessing Naturopathic and Siddha care can sometimes be challenging due to limited availability or awareness of practitioners. By leveraging the capabilities of natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning, the chatbot will interact with users in a conversational manner, making the system intuitive and user-friendly. Users will be able to describe their symptoms, medical history, and preferences to receive personalized treatment recommendations. Additionally, the chatbot will include a symptom checker to assess the user's health condition and provide relevant information on naturopathy and siddha treatments and remedies. One of the key features of the system is its integration with a doctor appointment booking system. This will allow users to schedule appointments with naturopathy doctors based on their availability and location, streamlining the process of seeking treatment. Overall, the project aims to improve access to naturopathy treatment and enhance the overall healthcare experience for users seeking natural and holistic healthcare solutions.

2. Existing System:

In existing system, implement Question Answering (QA) systems which can be identified as information accessing systems which try to answer to natural language queries by giving answers suitable answers making a use of attribute available in natural language techniques. The system takes a plain text as input and answering all type of questions output by qualified user is the output. Synchronous written conversations (or "chats") are becoming increasingly popular as Web-based mental health interventions. This review is based on an evaluation of individual synchronous Web-based chat technologies. Through the current evidence of the application of this technology, the tentative support for mode of intervention is seen. Interventions utilizing text-based synchronous communication showed better outcomes compared with Waitlist conditions and overall equivalent outcomes compared with Treatment As usual, and were at least as good as the comparison interventions. However, the issue of whether these technologies are cost effective in clinical practice remains a consideration for future research studies. Medical search has several unique requirements that distinguish itself from traditional Web search. However, existing medical Web search engines are optimized for precision and concentrate their search results on a few topics. This lack-of-diversity problem is aggravated by the nature of medical Web pages. When discussing a medical topic, many medical Web sites use similar, but not identical, descriptions by paraphrasing contents in medical textbooks and research papers

Disadvantages of Existing System:

- Difficult to extracting knowledge from the medical crowd-sourced Q&A websites.

- Irrelevant question-answer pairs may be extracted.
- The questions asked by patients can be noisy and ambiguous.

3. Proposed System:

The proposed system is a chatbot-based platform for naturopathy and siddha treatment, designed to provide users with personalized healthcare recommendations and facilitate doctor appointments. The system utilizes natural language processing (NLP) techniques to engage users in conversations, allowing them to describe their symptoms, medical history, and preferences. Based on this information, the chatbot generates personalized treatment plans using a database of Naturopathy and Siddha treatments and remedies. One of the key features of the system is its integration with a symptom checker, which enables users to assess their health condition and receive initial guidance on potential treatments. Additionally, the system includes a doctor appointment booking system, allowing users to schedule appointments with Naturopathy and Siddha doctors based on their availability and location. The system also provides educational content on naturopathy and holistic health practices, empowering users to make informed decisions about their health. Overall, the proposed system aims to enhance accessibility to naturopathy healthcare services and improve health outcomes for users

Proposed Block Diagram:

A system architecture can comprise system components, the externally visible properties of those components, the relationships (e.g. the behaviour) between them. It can provide a plan from which products can be procured, and systems developed, that will work together to implement the overall system

A. Modules:

- Interface Creation
- Post Questions
- Keyword Extraction
- Top K Results
- Text to Voice Conversion

B. Hardware Specification:

- Processor : Dual core processor 2.6.0 GHZ
- RAM : 4GB
- Hard disk : 320 GB
- Compact Disk : 650 Mb
- Keyboard : Standard

C. Software Specification:

- Operating system : Windows OS
- Front End : Python
- Back end : MYSQL Server
- Tool : Pycharm

D. Software Description:

- Python is an interpreted language, which precludes the need to compile code before executing a program because Python does the compilation in the background. Because Python is a high-level

programming language, it abstracts many sophisticated details from the programming code. Python focuses so much on this abstraction that its code can be understood by most novice programmers.

- Python code tends to be shorter than comparable codes. Although Python offers fast development times, it lags slightly in terms of execution time. Compared to fully compiling languages like C and C++, Python programs execute slower. Of course, with the processing speeds of computers these days, the speed differences are usually only observed in benchmarking tests, not in real-world operations. In most cases, Python is already included in Linux distributions and Mac OS X machines.

4. Applications:

- **Healthcare Accessibility:** The system can improve access to Naturopathy and Siddha healthcare services, especially in remote or underserved areas where access to traditional healthcare facilities may be limited.
- **Remote Patient Monitoring:** The chatbot can be used for remote patient monitoring, allowing healthcare providers to monitor patients' health status and provide timely interventions.
- **Chronic Disease Management:** The system can assist in the management of chronic diseases by providing patients with personalized treatment plans and monitoring their progress over time.
- **Health Education:** The chatbot can be used as an educational tool to provide information about Naturopathy and Siddha treatments and holistic health practices, helping users make informed decisions about their health

5. Advantages:

- **Accessibility:** The system improves access to Naturopathy and Siddha healthcare services by providing a convenient and user-friendly platform for users to interact with.
- **Personalization:** The system provides personalized treatment recommendations based on individual health needs and preferences, enhancing the effectiveness of naturopathy treatments.
- **Efficiency:** The system streamlines the process of seeking Naturopathy and Siddha care by integrating a doctor appointment booking system, reducing wait times and improving overall healthcare efficiency.
- **Education:** The system provides educational content on naturopathy and holistic health practices, empowering users to take control of their health and make informed decisions.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** The system offers a cost-effective alternative to traditional healthcare services, reducing the need for in-person consultations and appointments.

6. Result and Discussion:

The developed chatbot-based system for Naturopathy and Siddha treatment successfully achieved its objectives, providing users with personalized treatment recommendations and facilitating doctor appointments.

Name	Gender	Age	Email	Mobile	Address	Specialist	UserName	Appointment
san	male	20	san@gmail.com	9003578390	no	Heart	san	Appointment

7. Output:

8. Future Scope:

In the future, the bot's symptom recognition and diagnosis performance could be greatly improved by adding support for more medical features, such as location, duration, and intensity of symptoms, and more detailed symptom description. In future, we can extend the approach to implement various multi classification algorithms to improve the accuracy. And also includes other details such as operation procedures, videos with materials and so on.

9. Conclusion:

In this system we build up a system which is useful for medical institute or hospitals to help the users to freely ask medical dosage related queries by voice. System gets output for medicine API and speaks out and displays all medicine names. We are using NLP because we want to a computer to communicate with users in their terms. Large amount of data which is too diverse and complex to be evaluated by traditional methods are being generated by the health care transactions. The application of data mining on medical data can focus on new, useful and potentially lifesaving knowledge. The extraction or mining process of knowledge from the large amount of data is said to be data mining. It is considered as an innovation which tends to help the physicians who deal with large amount of data. A medical chatbot provides personalized diagnoses based on symptoms

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